

STRENGTHENING CLINICAL TRIAL REGULATORY AND ETHICAL REVIEW OVERSIGHT IN EAST AFRICA.

Authors: Xuemei Cui and Vivian Nchanchou Mbanya

Editor:

D1.2 Project Management Manual

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Contributor(s):	
Reviewer(s):	Rosemarie Bernabe
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ABSTRACT:	
Keyword List:	

Consortium:

	ROLE	NAME	Short Name	Country
1.	Coordinator	University of Oslo	UiO	Norway
2.	Partner	Uganda National Health Research Organization	UNHRO	Uganda
3.	Partner	Jimma University	JU	Ethiopia
4.	Partner	Uganda National Council for Science and Technology	UNCST	Uganda
5.	Partner	The National Drug Authority	NDA	Uganda
6.	Partner			
7.	Partner			
8.	Partner			

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1 Introduction

The aim of this project management manual is to provide a clear guideline for the consortiums in daily project activities, to set up rules and responsibilities of the consortiums and to ensure good quality and progress of the work.

This document will be updated when necessary, through the lifecycle of AccessAfrica2 project extending the information given, including relevant issues and changes in the project or procedures. Each time the document is updated, all partners will be duly informed about the updates and the changes made with respect to the previous version.

2 General Information

2.1 Project Participants

The list of Project Participants is included in the Grant Agreement, in the Consortium Agreement, and presented in Table1.

Table 1 List of participant organization

No	Participant Organization Name	Short Name	Country
1	University of Oslo	UiO	Norway
2	Uganda National Health Research Organization	UNHRO	Uganda
3	Jimma University	JU	Ethiopia
4	Uganda National Council for Science and Technology	UNCST	Uganda
5	The National Drug Authority	NDA	Uganda

2.2 Contact Person

Table 2 Contact list

	Scientific Contact	Admin/Finance Contact
UiO	*Rosemarie de La Cruz Bernabe (Project Coordinator) r.de.l.c.bernabe@medisin.uio.no Vivian Nchanchou Mbanya v.n.mbanya@medisin.uio.no	Xuemei Cui Xuemei.cui@medisin.uio.no Caroline Marianne Nielsen Nes c.m.n.nes@medisin.uio.no
UNHRO	*Bernard Kikaire (Project Scientific Coordinator) bkikaire@uvri.go.ug	Johnson Tumusiime jtumusiime@uvri.go.ug
JU	*Gudina Terefe Tucho gudina.terefe@ju.edu.et	Mintamir Mekasha mintimekasha@yahoo.com

UNCST	*Christopher Ddamulira c.ddamulira@uncst.go.ug Beth Mutumba b.mutumba@uncst.go.ug Hellen Opolot h.naluyima@uncst.go.ug	Faridah Nakabanda f.nakabanda@uncst.go.ug
NDA	*Helen Ndagije hndagije@nda.or.ug David Walusimbi dwalusimbi@nda.or.ug Diana Kesi Nakitto dnakitto@nda.or.ug Joyce Batera jbatera@nda.or.ug	Peter Kitooke pkitooke@nda.or.ug

* is the main contact person of each organization.

2.3 Project duration, budget, and EC Contribution

The effective start of the project is 01 July 2023, and the project ends 36 months later, on 30 June 2026.

The first reporting period (P1) is M1- M18, namely 01 July 2023 - 31 December 2024; the second reporting period (P2) is M19-M36, namely 01 January 2025 – 30 June 2026.

The project has an overall budget of 600 000 €, of which a maximum of 600 000 € shall be financed by the European Commission.

Table 3 Estimated budget for the action

	Personnel costs	Purchase costs		Indirect costs	Total costs	Max grant amount
		Travel	Other goods, works and services			
UiO	163 170.00	3 711.80	0	41 720.45	208 602.25	208 602.25
UNHRO	53 728.20	5 250.00	11 250.00	17 557.05	87 785.25	87 785.25
JU	44 200.00	11 540.00	28 900.00	21 160.00	105 800.00	105 800.00
UNCST	50 400.00	5 500.00	22 250.00	19 537.50	97 687.50	97 687.50
NDA	57 600	5 000.00	17 500.00	20 025.00	100 125.00	100 125.00
Total					600 000.00	600 000.00

3 Legal Documents

3.1 Grant Agreement (GA)

Grant Agreement NO. 101103296 is the contractual document signed by all the project partnership which defines the rights and obligations of the Consortium. The Grant Agreement comprises the following Annexes:

Annex 1 Description of the action

Annex 2 Estimated budget for the action

Annex 2a Additional information on unit costs and contributions (if applicable)

Annex 3 Accession forms (if applicable)

Annex 3a Declaration on joint and several liability of affiliated entities (if applicable)

Annex 4 Model for the financial statements

Annex 5 Specific rules (if applicable)

The Grant Agreement and its annexes is available for all the partners in the project Teams.

3.2 Consortium Agreement (CA)

The consortium Agreement is the internal contract of the consortium partners, which is accepted and signed by all the partners.

The CA came into force with the start of the project on 01 July 2023. It is also available in the project Teams.

3.3 Supporting documents

- **Annotated Grant Agreement (AGA)** for Horizon Europe. This is a user guide explaining all articles of the Grant Agreement providing examples and sample calculations.
This document is available at: [aga_en.pdf \(europa.eu\)](#)
- **Horizon Europe Online Manual.** This is an online user guide for EU funding and managing projects in Horizon Europe.
It is available at: [Online Manual - Online Manual - Funding Tenders Opportunities \(europa.eu\)](#)

- **Horizon Europe reporting template.** This template in PDF includes both technical report Part A (modules in the portal) and technical report Part B. It is available here: [periodic-report_horizon-euratom_en.pdf \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/erasmus-plus/en/actions/reporting/periodic-report-horizon-euratom-en.pdf)

4 Project Structure

4.1 Work Package (WP) list/overview

AccessAfrica2 project is a 36-month project organized in the following WPs. The detailed description of each WP is described in the Annex 1, DoA. Each WP has a named WP leader who is in charge of the leadership and coordination of the technical and economic aspects of the WP.

Table 4 List of Work packages and the staff effort

WP	WP name	Lead Ben	PM	Start Month	End Month
WP1	Coordination and Management	UiO	38	1	36
WP2	Improving regulatory and ethical review and oversight of clinical trials	NDA	36	1	36
WP3	Strengthening linkages between regulatory authorities and ethics review committees	UNCST	38	1	36
WP4	Increasing capacity of research leadership in SSA	JU	32	1	36

Table5 Staff effort per participant

Staff effort per participant					
<i>Grant Preparation (Work packages - Effort screen) — Enter the info.</i>					
Participant	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	Total Person-Months
1 - UiO	18.00	1.00		3.00	22.00
2 - UNHRO	8.00	2.00	2.00	4.00	16.00
3 - JU	4.00	4.00	4.00	22.00	34.00
4 - UNCST	3.00	8.00	22.00	3.00	36.00
5 - NDA	5.00	21.00	10.00		36.00
Total Person-Months	38.00	36.00	38.00	32.00	144.00

4.2 Deliverables

Each WP will have associated deliverables. The list of deliverables is shown in the Table 6.

All the deliverables identified in Annex 1 to the Grant Agreement have to be submitted to the EC according to the timetable specified in the list.

3 months before the due date, the project coordinator will send a reminder to the one who is responsible for that deliverable. Latest 2 weeks before the due date, a decent draft of the deliverable has to be sent to internal reviewers. Latest 1 week before the due date, a final version has to be sent to the project coordinator and the scientific coordinator for approval. The coordinator is responsible for uploading the final PDF version in the participant portal.

Table6 List of the deliverables

WP	NO.	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary	Due Date
WP1	D1.1	Project website	UiO	30 Sep 2023
WP1	D1.2	Project Management Manual	UiO	30 Jun 2024
WP1	D1.3	Hold annual General Meetings	UNHRO	30 Jun 2024
WP1	D1.4	Data Management Plan	UiO	31 Dec 2023
WP1	D1.5	Exploitation and dissemination plan	UiO	31 Dec 2023
WP1	D1.6	Updated Data Management Plan	UiO	30 Jun 2025
WP1	D1.7	Updated exploitation and dissemination plan	UiO	30 Jun 2025
WP2	D2.1	Recruitment of 2 regulatory officers	NDA	30 Sep 2023
WP2	D2.2	Safety monitoring system development	NDA	30 Jun 2024
WP2	D2.3	Joint Inspections conduct	NDA	30 Jun 2024
WP2	D2.4	Report from desk review of RAs and IRBs	NDA	30 Jun 2024
WP2	D2.5	Develop a clinical trial operational manual for NDA	NDA	30 Jun 2024
WP2	D2.6	Publish summarized evaluation reports of clinical trial applications	NDA	30 Jun 2024
WP3	D3.1	Joint review guidelines development and approval	UNCST	31 Dec 2023
WP3	D3.2	Final proposal for COVID 19 survey	UNCST	29 Feb 2024
WP3	D3.3	Development and roll out the guidelines and framework to Ethiopia partners	UNCST	30 Sep 2024
WP3	D3.4	Final joint review guidelines and framework	UNCST	31 Dec 2024
WP3	D3.5	Final report of the COVID 19 Survey	UNCST	30 Jun 2025
WP3	D3.6	Launch of joint review guidelines and framework in Ethiopia	UNCST	30 Jun 2025
WP3	D3.7	Publications from the COVID 19 survey	UNCST	31 May 2026
WP3	D3.8	Dissemination of the results from the situation analysis	UNCST	30 Jun 2026
WP4	D4.1	Training Manual on research leadership	JU	31 Aug 2024
WP4	D4.2	Training Manual on Ethics capacity	JU	31 Dec 2024
WP4	D4.3	3 training workshops in Ethiopia	JU	31 Dec 2024

4.3 Milestones

Each WP will have associated Milestones. The list of milestones is shown in the following table. 3 months before the due date, the project coordinator will send a reminder to the one who is responsible for that milestone. A simple document showing the accomplishment of the milestone is required.

Table 7 List of the Milestones

	Milestone	WP	Lead Beneficiary	Due date
1	Meeting schedule (Project management body), quarterly meetings/Teleconferences for WP1 and other WPs developed and circulated	WP1	UNHRO	31 Oct 2023
2	Quarterly WP1 meetings	WP1	UNHRO	30 Sep 2023
3	A running Safety monitoring system	WP2	NDA	30 Jun 2024
4	Solitary Interlinked system	WP2	NDA	31 Aug 2024
5	Joint inspections conducted	WP2	NDA	31 Dec 2024
6	Proposal approval	WP3	UNCST	31 Dec 2023
7	Approval/Launch of the joint review guidelines	WP3	UNCST	30 Jun 2024
8	Approval/launch of the joint inspection framework	WP3	UNCST	31 Dec 2024
9	At least 2 training manuals are available for training	WP4	JU	31 Dec 2024
10	At least 90% of the planned trainee will be trained in scientific leadership and ethics capacity	WP4	JU	30 Nov 2025

5 Project Management

The basic purpose of project management is to ensure the proper level of co-ordination and cooperation amongst the project consortium members and timely reporting to the European Commission. The partners involved have agreed on developing an effective and decentralized management structure based on delegated responsibilities. AccessAfrica2 project management system will provide full transparency and control of the entire project in terms of time, resources, and cost tracking.

5.1 Project management structure

Project operation will involve the following roles or groups: (a) General Assembly, (b) Steering board, (c) Work Package Leaders, (d) External Advisory Board. The mandate and the scope of these roles and groups are described below. The decision-making authority has been divided between the General Assembly and the Steering board to ensure open and fair decision-making, while allowing for agile project management and time-efficient monitoring of the progress.

- ***The General Assembly (GA)***

Role: The GA is the supreme decision-making body of the project and is responsible for the major strategic and scientific decisions. The GA has one representative from each of the project partners. It is chaired by the coordinator. The GA will monitor the status regarding the scientific progress, costs, quality and compare the current and planned status. The GA will convene at the annual project meeting, to revise and update the plans for these aspects for the upcoming year. Further, the GA will monitor the knowledge gained and the project risks. If needed, updates will be made and actions will be taken regarding these issues. In particular, the GA will be responsible for the issues listed below:

- Review the scientific progress and costs incurred so far
- Re-distribute tasks and/or budget within the consortium, if necessary
- Decide whether requests for contract amendments are to be made, if necessary
- Adopt a scientific work plan for the upcoming year
- Review the dissemination and communication activities so far, compare to the plan and adopt a dissemination/communication plan for the upcoming year
- Review the quality of the work and results so far
- Review the project risks and adopt of an updated risk response plan based on the project so far and identification of potentially emerging new risks
- Resolve conflicts related to the project activities, if these can't be resolved at a lower level
- Decide on changes in the Consortium Agreement, if necessary

- ***The steering board***

Role: The steering board consists of the coordinator and the WP leaders. The coordinator is the chair of the steering board. The steering board oversees the day-to-day management of the project activities, in particular:

- Track and monitor progress of the WP activities
- Monitor potential deviations from the work plans and report them to the GA
- Manage scientific, dissemination/communication activities in line with the yearly plans adopted by the GA
- Take initiative on mitigating actions in line with the risk response plan
- Ensure sufficient communication between the WPs to obtain seamless interfaces between them
- Facilitate resolution of conflict

- ***The coordinator and the support team***

Role: The coordinator and the support team is the link between the project partners and the European Commission. They will be responsible for the proper performance of the tasks as described in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. In particular:

- Provide any document or information required by the EC
- Timely Submission of deliverables and periodic and final reports to the EC
- Manage the payments to the members of the Consortium
- Organize yearly GA meetings, Steering Board meetings and External Advisory Board meetings
- Ensure that the governing documents and other important project internal information are available on the project Teams.

- ***The Work Package Leaders (WPLs)***

Role: The WPLs are responsible for the daily progress of the WP activities. The WPLs manage the work within the WP assigned to them in accordance with the Grant Agreement. The WPLs will in particular:

- Take actions to ensure satisfactory progress of the WP activities
- Initiate meetings within the WP when needed
- Initiate meetings between WPs when needed
- Participate in the steering board meetings

- ***The External Advisory Board (EAB)***

Role: The EAB will be consulted and to provide advice on matters pertaining to the running and the direction of the consortium. EAB may also be asked to comment on matters pertaining to the scientific work or ethical issues arising in the project.

5.2 Meetings

Meetings schedule during the project period is listed in table 8.

Note:

- Meeting agenda, minutes, and *signature from the participants when meeting in person* is mandatory! This applies to all kinds of the meetings.

- Invitation of GA will be sent 30 calendar days prior to the meeting and the agenda will be distributed 21 days prior to the meeting.

Table 8 AA2 meeting schedule

Management Body	Frequency	Schedule
General Assembly	At least once a year	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1st Meeting, 18 Jul 2023, Online • Kick Off, 20-21 Sep 2023, Uganda, • GA, 26 Jun 2024, Online • GA 4-5 Sep 2024, Uganda (Scheduled) • GA autumn 2025 (Planned) • GA before summer 2026 (Planned)
Steering Board Meeting	Monthly	
External Advisory Board Meeting	To be updated	

6 Project reporting and payment

6.1 Reporting obligations

During the AccessAfrica2 project implementation, three types of report are scheduled:

- **Internal reports:** Partners submit a financial report with costs breakdown to the coordinator. The coordinator will check the alignment of all tasks and resources used.
- **EC periodic report.** This includes both technical and financial report. The coordinator will ensure alignment of all tasks and resources used before submitting the report to the EC.
- **EC continues report:** Continues report interacts with periodic report. All the partners are requested to keep track on their dissemination and communication activities in a daily basis – by putting the activity into the template of dissemination and communication list once the activity occurs. This template is in line with the periodic report in the participant portal and it can be found in the project Teams.
-

6.2 Reporting calendar

To ensure the submission of the report to the EC on time, all partners must respect the submission dates in Table9.

Table 9 Reporting due dates

Reporting type	Months	Period covered	Submission date to the coordinator	Final submission date to EC
Internal Report	M9	01 Jul 2023 - 31 Mar 2024	30 Apr 2024	-
Periodic Report	M18	01 Jul 2023 - 31 Dec 2024	31 Jan 2025	28 Feb 2025
Internal Report	M27	01 Jan 2025 - 30 Sep 2025	31 Oct 2025	-
Final Report	M36	01 Jan 2025 - 31 Jul 2026	31 Aug 2026	30 Sep 2026

6.3 Pre - payment

As agreed in the consortium agreement, for UNHRO, UNCST and NDA, 60% on receipt of the pre-financing will be transferred to the partners immediately in M1. The rest 40% will be transferred after the coordinator has received and assessed the technical and financial input for the first internal report (M1-M9) from the partners.

As agreed, for JU, 30% on receipt of the pre-financing will be transferred to JU immediately in M1. The rest 70% will be transferred after the coordinator has received and assessed the technical and financial input for the first internal report (M1-M9) either at once or several times depending on the progress and resource usage.

Table 10 Payment schedule of the per-financing

	Total Grant	Pre-Payment	Pre-Payment transferred	After M9
Uio	208 602,25	114 731,24	114 731,24	0
UNHRO	87 785,25	48 281,89	28 969,13	19 312,76
JU	105 800,00	58 190,00	17 457,00	Depends
UNCST	97 687,50	53 728,13	32 236,88	21 491,25
NDA	100 125,00	55 068,75	33 041,25	22 027,50
Total	600 000,00	330 000,00		

6.4 Payment schedule

The coordinator will transfer the payments from the EC to the partners after the reports are accepted.

Table 11 Payment schedule during the project period

Time	Payment Type	Comments
M1	Part of the Pre-financing (60% or 30%)	
After M9	Rest of the Pre-financing	
After M20	1st EC interim payment	After the P1 report is accepted
After M38	Final balance and payment of Guarantee Fund	After the final report is accepted

7 Communication

7.1 Communication with the European Commission

The project coordinator is responsible for an efficient communication between the consortium and the EC. Any messages from the partners to the commission shall pass through the project coordinator. This means that the partners shall not directly contact the project officer. The coordinator shall always contact the project officer through the communication center in the participant portal. For emergency cases, an email to the project officer can be followed up.

7.2 Internal communication (platform)

The project Teams will be the main platform for internal communication and document storage. All the members are expected to use Teams to work on documents, store documents, post messages, assign tasks, send reminders, etc. Besides, emails can also be used.

7.3 Labelling documents

Please use the following labels for documents.

Table 12 Labeling of documents

Type	Label	Example
Emails	AA2 + subject	AA2, Invitation for the Kick-off meeting
Documents	YYMMDD_AA2_name	240601_AA2_Template
Deliverables	Del No_AA2_Del name	D1.2_AA2_Managment Manual

7.4 Project Website

In order to properly reach the general public, the project website <https://www.accessafrica.uio.no/> will be continuously updated with project general information, news, deliverables, publications, consortium information, etc.

7.5 Social Media

The project has also an account in LinkedIn in order to better communicate the project activities and disseminate the outcomes of the project to different audiences:

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/accessafrica-2_if-you-would-like-to-learn-more-about-access-activity-7156271346547605504-IGIX?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

7.6 Acknowledgement

Any communication from the project must contain the project logo, the EU flag, the EDCTP3 logo and the following statement:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe under GA No 101103296. This project is supported by the Global Health EDCTP3 Joint Undertaking and its members.

Project logo:

EU flag:

EDCTP3 Logo:

8 Risk management

The following risk-mitigation measures will be observed for the risks identified during the preparation of the proposal.

Table 13 Risk and mitigation measurement

	Description	Mitigation Measurement
1	Failure for partners to provide technical and financial reports (low)	Frequent reminders and support to the partners during the reporting period to provide the reports in a timely manner
2	Failure of partners to execute their project mandate (low)	Regular WP and project management meetings to review progress and identify strategies for challenges in implementation of project activities
3	Financial (possible, medium)	Regular WP and project management meetings to review progress and identify strategies for challenges in implementation of project activities
4	System failure (possible, high)	Institute system backup procedures
5	Misappropriation of funds (Low)	Accountability of funds in time and regular audit by the UNCST internal auditor

6	Conflicts within the consortium (low)	Regular meetings will be held and agree on issues through open discussions
7	Low likelihood of physical training risk due to COVID 19	COVID 19 prevention measures will be used

9 Data Management Plan

In line with the established project objectives, the project will deliver the following time-bound and measurable outputs-

- Staff training reports in pharmacovigilance and clinical trial regulatory mechanisms.
- RA officers and REC members training in review and oversight of vaccine development studies.
- Development of a safety monitoring system to track trends in safety reporting.
- Report on joint inspections of clinical trials sites.
- A report from desk review of RAs and IRBs
- Guidelines for joint review of clinical trials in Uganda
- Framework for joint review of clinical trial in Ethiopia

Management of project data

The data types to be collected by ACCESSAFRICA 2 are diverse. These data include data from the review of documentation, personal data from interviews and survey, personal data from stakeholder consultation meetings, workshops and inspections—including expert stakeholders, other data from training materials and guidelines.

Fair data

ACCESSAFRICA 2 work packages must leverage all data gathered according to the purposes outlined in the ACCESSAFRICA 2 Description of Action. Partners involved in ACCESSAFRICA 2 should rigorously adhere to FAIR principles and data protection regulations.

Generated Data:

- All data generated must adhere to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable).
- Researchers are required to strive to make all data collected as open as possible, respecting any necessary restrictions.

Additionally, unless restricted by privacy, confidentiality concerns, or General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) requirements, the data will be published in FAIR data repositories like Zenodo following a thorough curation process.

Data security

During the project timeframe, all researchers involved in data collection are required to:

- Securely store the data in full compliance with GDPR regulations.
- Gather and manage the data generated in ACCESSAFRICA 2 according to their respective institution's regulatory specifications.

Data protection and anonymization

- Audio Files: Audio files requiring anonymization during transcription should be deleted after verification.
- Data Anonymization: All data must be anonymized unless participants provide informed consent or in cases where anonymization is not feasible.
- Data Linkage: The project will not maintain a link between anonymized data and the original identifiable participant data.
- Data Analysis: All data analysis will be conducted exclusively using anonymized data.
- Data Sharing: Only anonymized data will be deposited in data repositories at the project's conclusion.

Sharing of project results

A data-sharing agreement, signed by all ACCESSAFRICA 2 partners, will address the rights for disseminating and exploiting intellectual property and know-how. Additionally, the jointly developed guidelines from this project will be made available to enhance research ethics capacity and research leadership across Sub-Saharan Africa.